

Artificial Intelligence based Pattern Recognition

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence based pattern recognition is one of the most important tools in process control to identify process problems. The objective of this study was to evaluate the relative performance of a feature-based Recognizer compared with the raw data-based recognizer. The study focused on recognition of seven commonly researched patterns plotted on the quality chart. The artificial intelligence based pattern recognizer trained using the three selected statistical features resulted in significantly better performance compared with the raw data-based recognizer.

Keywords-- CCP, Neural Network Configuration, ANN

I. INTRODUCTION

There are seven basic CCPs, e.g. normal (NOR), systematic (SYS), cyclic (CYC), increasing trend (IT), decreasing trend (DT), upward shift(US) and downward shift (DS) [6]. All other patterns are either special forms of basic CCPs or mixed forms of two or more basic CCPs. Only the NOR pattern is indicative of a process continuing to operate under controlled condition [6]. All other CCPs are unnatural and associated with impending problems.. ANN learns to recognize patterns directly through a typical sample patterns during a training phase. Neural nets may provide required abilities to replace the human operator. Neural network also have the ability to

identify an arbitrary Pattern not previously encountered. Back propagation network (BPN) has been widely used to recognize different abnormal patterns of a control chart [1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10].BPN is a supervised-learning network and its output value is continuous, usually between [0, 1]. It is usually used for detecting, forecasting and classification tasks, and is one of the most commonly used networks [3].

II. PATTERN RECOGNIZER DESIGN

2.1 Sample Patterns

Sample patterns should be collected from a real manufacturing process. Since, a large number of patterns are required for developing and validating a CCP recognizer, and as those are not economically available, simulated data are often used.

2.2 Sample Patterns for Statistical Features

The choice of statistical features to be extracted from the raw data to be presented as the input vector into the recognizer is very important. The presence of too many input features can burden the training process and lead to inefficient recognizers. Features low in information content or redundant should be eliminated whenever possible. Redundant here refers to features with marginal contribution given that other features are present. [5, 8, 9, 14].

Table 1: Pair wise correlation coefficients between statistical features

	mean	median	mode
mean	1	0.9566	0.7410
median	0.9566	1	0.6773
mode	0.7410	0.6733	1

2.3 Training Algorithms

It is very difficult to know which training algorithm will be the fastest for a given problem. It depends on many factors, including the complexity of the problem, the number of data points in the training set, the number of weights and biases in the network, the error goal, and this section compares the various training algorithms.

2.4 Neural Network Configuration

The recognizer was developed based on multilayer perceptions (MLPs) architecture; its structure comprises an input layer, one or more hidden layer(s) and an output layer. Figure 1 shows an MLP neural network structure comprising these layers and their respective weight connections.

Figure1. MLP neural network architecture

Table2: Targeted recognizer outputs

Pattern class	Recognizer outputs node						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
NOR	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
SYS	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
CYC	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
DT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
US	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
DS	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

2.4.1 ANN Configuration for Raw Data

Network details: traindx

Architecture: 32-16-7 network, with tansig TF and logsig TF in hidden and output layer respectively. Training: traindx algorithm

TRAINDX

NNHL: number of neurons in hidden layer

Figure2. NNHL VS R

2.4.2 ANN Configuration for Statistical Features

Network details: traindx

Architecture: 6-12-7 network, with tansig TF and logsig TF in hidden and output layer respectively. Training: traindx algorithm

TRAINDX

NNHL: number of neurons in hidden layer

Figure3. NNHL VS R

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

ANN recognizers was developed using raw data and statistical features as the input vector. This section

discusses the procedures for the training and recall (recognition) phases of the recognizers.

3.1 Training Phase

The overall procedure began with the generation and presentation of process data to the observation window. All patterns were fully developed when they appeared within the recognition window. For raw data as the input vector, the pre-processing stage involved basic transformation into standardized Normal (0, 1) values [5]. Before the sample data were presented to the ANN for the learning process, it was divided into training (60%), validation (20%) and preliminary testing (20%) sets [4]. These sample sets were then randomized to avoid possible bias in the presentation order of the sample patterns to the ANN. The training procedure was conducted iteratively covering ANN learning, validation of in-training ANN and preliminary testing. During learning, a training data set (2100 patterns) was used for updating the network weights and biases. The ANN was then subjected to in-training validation using the validation data set (700 patterns) for early stopping to avoid over fitting. The error on the validation set will typically begin to rise when the network begins to over fit the data. The training process was stopped when the validation error increases for a specified number of iterations. In this study, the maximum number of validation failures was set to five iterations. The ANN was then subjected to preliminary performance tests using the testing data set (700 patterns). The training was stopped whenever one of the following stopping criteria was satisfied. The performance error goal was achieved, the maximum allowable number of training epochs was met or the maximum number of validation failures was exceeded (validation test). Once the training stopped, the trained recognizer was evaluated for acceptance. The recognizer would be retrained using a totally new data set if its performance remained poor. This procedure was intended to minimize the effect of poor training sets. Each type of recognizer was replicated by exposing them to 3 different training cycles, giving rise to 3 different trained recognizers for early stopping and 3 different trained recognizers without early stopping. All 6 recognizers in training algorithms have the same architecture and differ only in the training data sets used. Discussion on the training and recall performance provided in table 3 are given in section 4.

3.2 Recall or Recognition Phase

Once accepted, the trained recognizer was tested (recall phase) using 3 different sets of fresh totally unseen data sets of size 3500 each. Results of the recall phase are presented in the table 3&4 and discussed in section 4. Train the network without early stopping and with early stopping for the selected algorithms and the results are tabulated and discussed in section 4.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents results and comparisons of the performance between the feature-based recognizers trained and tested using the three recommended statistical features as given in section 2 and the recognizers trained and tested using raw data. It was noted during training that feature-based recognizers were more easily trained.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this study was to evaluate the relative performance of training algorithms with the optimum structure for raw data and statistical features based optimized CCP recognizer. Feature based recognizers achieved a statistically significant improvement in recognition performance. Further, the use of the statistical feature set required less training effort and resulted in better recall performance. The MLP neural network was used as a generic recognizer to classify seven different types of SPC chart patterns. In this study five training algorithms are studied for generalization with early stopping and without early stopping and traindx is identified to be the best algorithm for this particular problem.

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